

(RESEARCH ARTICLE)

Marketing strategy of bottled drinking water “envoz” with transformative learning

Luki Sri Anggoro Wati * and Listyowati Puji Rahayu

Department of Management, Faculty of Economics and Business, Boyolali University, Central Java - Indonesia.

World Journal of Advanced Research and Reviews, 2024, 23(02), 2339–2344

Publication history: Received on 17 July 2024; revised on 24 August 2024; accepted on 26 August 2024

Article DOI: <https://doi.org/10.30574/wjarr.2024.23.2.2530>

Abstract

Envoz is one of the Bottled Drinking Water (AMDK) products that is processed with 30 juz Qur'an murottal readings every day for 24 hours without stopping. In addition, other treatments are given, namely with the addition of oxygen which is believed to make the body healthier and stronger. This paper aims to find out the marketing concept of the Envazz brand targeting consumers in Central Java. This research uses a field approach. Data sources are obtained through interviews, observation and documentation. The results showed that the marketing carried out by AMDK Brand Envoz was based on transformative learning, where in each marketing was designed to foster awareness and desire of the public personally to consume healthy water. This is because in transformational learning, the best motivation to do something comes from internal or self.

Keywords: Transformative; Marketing; Bottled; Drinking; Water

1. Introduction

Communication comes from the word communis which means togetherness or can be interpreted by building togetherness between several people. The word communication in Latin is taken from the root word Comunico which means to share (Rizaldi & Hidayat, 2020). Communication in the process is divided into two, namely: primary communication process and secondary communication process. The primary communication process is the delivery of communication using symbols or media to other people. The media used is media that can be translated directly, so that communicators understand what communicators think. These media include language, gestures, images, colours, and others. The primary communication process runs directly without using tools. While the secondary communication process is the process of conveying information from the communicator to the communicant by using a second medium such as tools or means in the modern world, such as tools in the form of smartphones (Zein & Wagiaty, 2023).

Marketing is a way to satisfy the needs of buyers by designing systematically from planning to determining the price of the products being sold. Not only that, marketing also plans how goods are promoted, and distributed to buyers (Haris et al., 2023). Marketing is also defined as a process for offering, creating, and exchanging a product that has value to individuals or groups using managerial and social processes (Batoebara et al., 2023). Marketing communication is an activity or activity that aims to influence, persuade by spreading communication, so as to increase the target market which will cause people to accept, be loyal, or buy from a product or company (Iswati et al., 2023).

Transformative learning is a learning process that aims to make basic changes that occur in learners. In Webster Dictionary, transformative means, changing a form, both in appearance and structure; changing a condition, both in character and nature; and changing a substance (Meerts-Brandtsma et al., 2020). Transformative theory is a learning process that initially has an inappropriate frame of reference to become more tolerant, inclusive, open, relative, and able to change emotional conditions. Transformative learning begins with someone who experiences confusion in the direction of an activity, which makes someone doubt what they believe to be right or wrong, thus making someone a

* Corresponding author: Luki Sri Anggoro Wati

personal crisis. This personal or self-crisis will make people confirm the truth they believe to others (Iafate, 2018). Because a personal or self-crisis can affect the development of a person's self-concept formation, an active discussion with others is needed, in order to confirm the truth that is believed or the frame of reference that a person believes in (Biasin, 2018).

Bottled drinking water circulating in the community has a variety of brands and types. Types of drinking water can be seen from the content and production process, these types include: first, mineral water, which is water that contains certain minerals in it. These minerals are purely produced by water and there is no addition of certain materials, this is in accordance with SNI 01-3553-2006 or its amendments. Mineral water consists of mineral water, carbonated water, and oxygenated water. In natural mineral water there must be no addition of oxygen (O₂) or carbon dioxide (CO₂). Secondly, demineralised water, is bottled drinking water produced from various processes such as deionisation, distillation, osmosis reservation. In the processing of mineral water, oxygen (O₂) or carbon dioxide (CO₂) may be added. The result of this treatment is water that does not contain minerals or contains low minerals. The process of deionisation or removal of ions in the water content is carried out without removing pathogens or contaminants in the water, so the level of water purity is influenced by the source of the water. Third, pure mineral water, is water obtained from drilling in the ground or from the mountains. To be consumed, pure mineral water does not require demineralisation, but it must still pass the test first. The water used is tasteless, odourless, and contains no chemical compounds.

Various AMDKs are competing in providing water quality balanced with their marketing concepts to win the hearts of consumers. The abundance of AMD brands in Indonesia makes companies must be able to innovate in marketing their products. Based on this description, this paper seeks to further explore the marketing concept of the Envazz brand of Bottled Drinking Water (AMDK).

2. Methods

This research uses a field approach. Data sources were obtained through interviews, observation and documentation. Secondary sources of material in this research are various literatures that directly discuss marketing communication and transformative learning. Triangulation data analysis was used in collecting data; data reduction process; presentation; and conclusion drawing.

3. Results and discussion

CV. Tirta Mekar Jaya (TMJ) produces water with the trademark Envov, which all forms of activities are carried out based on the Company's vision, namely implementing a business management system using adequate facilities and infrastructure. The advantage of Envov is that it is processed by reading the murottal of the Qur'an 30 juz every day for 24 hours without stopping. In addition, another treatment is given, namely the addition of oxygen which is believed to make the body healthier and stronger.

Marketing communication is a form of effort from companies to inform or introduce their products to the public. The introduction of products to the public aims to make people have information about products and persuade people to have the desire to buy the products they sell (Fadli et al., 2021). Marketing communication is also defined as an effort to achieve certain goals by using an aspect which consists of marketing aspects, namely: sales promotion, advertising, marketing public relations, and direct sales (Purnomo et al., 2019). Marketing communication is the use of various kinds of communication techniques that aim to market a product from a company to the public, so that people will have information about the products being sold, and increase the income or profit earned by the Company (Katti & Barbosa, 2023).

Marketing communication also aims to change various things about consumers' views on a product, namely changes in attitudes, changes in knowledge, and changes in desired actions. These change efforts use a variety of media or channels that can be used, in the modern era now many people advertise using social media, such as Facebook, Instagram, Tiktok, Youtube and so on (Marpurdianto & Kusuma, 2022).

Marketing communication is very important in various companies, because with the correct marketing communication it will make it easier for companies to achieve their goals (Permatasari & Adinugraha, 2021). Marketing communication can help companies deal with their consumers. With marketing communication, it can make it easier for companies to introduce products to their customers. Good marketing communication will strengthen the marketing strategy used by the company in introducing its products. So that business partners and consumers can interact with the Company regarding the products or services offered (Pahlevi & Nurcahyo, 2022).

The process of marketing communication must go through 4 (four) stages, namely: there is a source, encoding, transmission, and decoding (Susanti et al., 2023). The occurrence of the marketing communication process must begin with a source, where the source can be from advertising or occur through direct marketing personnel. Before marketing communication is carried out, it must already have goals, target markets, market segmentation, and positioning. This is used to determine the type or theme of the advertisement to be used. After that, carry out the encoding process, which is to create a message to tell the benefits of a product to be advertised, and do not forget to choose the type of advertisement to be used. Next do the transmission, which is conveying the message to the public who is the target market of the product using the media. The media used also adjusts the target market to be targeted, such as using radio, TV, newspapers, or for the current generation using social media such as Facebook, Instagram, Youtube, Tiktok and other social media. Messages are made so that they can reach the public. After the message reaches the community, it will cause various kinds of responses, both positive, negative and neutral. This response is called decoding. In its implementation, communication barriers must also be considered so that the message can be conveyed in accordance with the target market.

Transformative learning in its implementation can be developed to keep up with the times, but still pay attention to the basic values of transformative learning itself (Baumgartner, 2019). The basic thing to be a reference for developing transformative learning is to identify the key processes and their determinants. The communicative domain is the most significant process in transformative learning. It begins with identifying the subject matter, understanding values, knowing the initial perspective, testing assumptions, conducting dialogue using critical discourse, then arriving at the stage of taking conclusions based on the results of the discourse (Chao, 2017).

Transformation can be realised through 4 (four) processes or stages, namely: elaborating or improving the value or meaning scheme; studying or learning a new meaning scheme; making changes to the meaning scheme; and making changes to the meaning perspective (Schnitzler, 2020). The transformative learning process aims to transform learners (McRae, 2015).

Transformation of learners is realised through 5 (five) stages, namely: First, activating event, is an event or event that makes learners have an awareness of the deficiencies in terms of their understanding or knowledge. Second, learners have the opportunity or space to identify and actualise the various assumptions that underlie the learners' initial knowledge, Third, learners critically reflect on their initial assumptions. Fourth, conduct critical discourse, with discussion or dialogue. Fifth, having space or opportunities for learners to test and implement their new perspectives (Albeta et al., 2021).

Learning is a very complicated and broad process, because in the process learning is influenced by many factors, starting from the factors of educators, students, and the learning environment (SIVAGNANAM, 2016). Learning in general is a process in which there is interaction between students, educators, and infrastructure or media used in the process. The process has a goal to change a behaviour that is oriented to be better. Transformative achievement needs to pay attention to several external factors to make learning more effective. It also needs to be designed in such a way as to support, activate, and maintain some internal processes that occur in learning (Kaowiwattanakul, 2020).

Transformative learning is an attempt to transform frames of reference such as habits of mind, mindsets, perspectives, and sets of assumptions using a process. The process is done in order to change the problematic frame of reference to be more open, inclusive, sorting, reflective, and emotionally changed. With this process, the frame of reference can change for the better. This is because someone will know a more correct opinion when learning, and make someone able to be precise in determining attitudes or actions (Dix, 2016). Transformative learning occurs through several processes, namely: First, critically reflecting on various sources, characteristics and understanding the consequences of various assumptions, both assumptions that come from oneself and others. Second, using empirical research methods to determine the truth, so that in instrumental learning the right thing will be said to be true. Third, communicative learning aims to achieve confidence in the form of insightful and sustainable discourse so that it can be justified (Daramola, 2018).

A marketing communication process in its implementation requires a strategy, where the marketing communication strategy is used to achieve the objectives of marketing goals. The use of marketing strategies can determine the costs used for the marketing process so that product prices can also adjust. Strategic planning itself must be oriented towards the market and occur managerially to develop and maintain the objectives of the company itself and develop the capabilities of the organisation's resources so as not to be left behind with ever-changing market opportunities. Therefore, the long-term goals of the company must be the focus of marketing strategy, so that in achieving the goals of the company it is necessary to involve marketing programme planning (Muttaqin et al., 2022).

The stages of a marketing strategy include: first, marketing communication objectives. The first thing to do is to make the purpose of marketing communication itself, the goal can be to expand distribution, increase market share, or increase sales (Madan & Rosca, 2022). Second, segmentation and targeting. Segmentation is a process to find out the specific groups that companies can fulfil the wants or needs of their products. In determining segmentation, it is necessary to pay attention to several aspects, namely geographic, demographic, behavioural, psychological, and benefits. Targeting is the selection of consumer segments that will be the focus of the promotion or marketing process (Satriawan & Purnama, 2022). Third, referencing and positioning. Deference is needed to determine consumer needs, which can be done by making decisions about how to position and present products in a cooperative environment. Positioning is a way for target consumers to have an image or image of the products offered. It is intended that the products sold have more value or advantages compared to other products (Makgopa, 2022).

The transformative marketing strategies carried out by AMDK Envoy in each stage include: first, activating events. The company deliberately and systematically assesses the background of consumers, presenting different points of view in every marketing process. Consumers are always conditioned to disorient their dilemma, taking note of their shortcomings. AMDK Envoy in this case understands the public that the health requirements of bottled water include physical chemistry, microbiology, and radioactive. Water and Bottled Drinking Water have an important role for life so they need to be regulated in depth. Regulators can come from WHO, the State, or local governments. The definition of Bottled Drinking Water (AMDK) according to the Minister of Industry Regulation Number 49/M-IND/PER/3/2012 concerning the Enforcement of the Indonesian National Standard (SNI) for Bottled Drinking Water (AMDK) in Article 1 Paragraph 1, reads, 'Bottled Drinking Water, called AMDK, is water that has been processed without the use of other food ingredients or additional food ingredients, then packaged, and is safe to drink'.

Fourth, encourage critical discourse. The company conditions consumers to carry out questions and answers, which contain an analysis of the new paradigm and then compare it with their initial assumptions. AMDK Envoy in this case always routinely opens its companies through CV. Tirta Mekar Jaya (TMJ) in terms of teaching pupils or students to learn, either through internship programs or Field Work Practices (PKL). This continues to be done to strengthen and update knowledge that scientifically can be used as a record in Envoy product development. Fifth, provide space for testing new perspectives or paradigms. The company assigns tasks to consumers, by carrying out case enrichment, where consumers are asked to look for new perspectives and the consumer's willingness to express them. AMDK Envoy in this case opens wide communication on social media and directly for work visits and business discussions on Envoy development.

Learning from the industrial world's perspective in principle consists of two aspects in the process, namely learning and teaching, where these two aspects go hand in hand. So that in the process, the company as the provider of learning materials must know what to do, as do consumers or the public who are the recipients of the materials from the learning process.

4. Conclusion

Strategic planning must be market-oriented and occur managerially to develop and maintain the objectives of the Company itself and develop the capabilities of the organization's resources so as not to be left behind by ever-changing market opportunities. One approach that can be taken from transformative learning-based marketing at AMDK Envoy is rational-cognitive; where people transform their thought patterns and behavior (change in cognitive and behavior). The transformative learning process was chosen as a marketing concept considering its function in forming a complete human being, namely an individual who can be rational and analytical, especially in choosing healthy drinking water.

Compliance with ethical standards

Disclosure of conflict of interest

There is no conflict of interest to be disclosed.

References

- [1] Albeta, S. W., Haryati, S., Futra, D., Aisyah, R., & Desviana, A. (2021). The Effect of Learning Style on Students' Learning Performance During the Covid-19 Pandemic. *JTK: Jurnal Tadris Kimiya*, 6(1), 115–123.

- [2] Arbeiter, J., & Bucar, M. (2020). Transformative Education Bridging Education for Change. *European Union, July*. <https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.30182.96322>
- [3] Batoebara, M. U., Harahap, A. T., & Nasution, F. H. (2023). SOCIAL SCIENCE AND POLITICAL SCIENCE BUSINESS MARKETING COMMUNICATION IN THE DIGITAL ERA. *Journal of Proceedings*, 3(April), 241–246.
- [4] Baumgartner, L. (2019). Fostering Transformative Learning in Educational Settings. *Adult Literacy Education: The International Journal of Literacy, Language, and Numeracy*, 1(1), 69–74. <https://doi.org/10.35847/lbaumgartner.1.1.69>
- [5] Biasin, C. (2018). Transformative Learning: Evolutions of the adult learning theory (Apprentissage Transformateur: les évolutions de la théorie de l'apprentissage des adultes). *Phronesis*, 7(3), 5–17. <http://id.erudit.org/iderudit/1054404ar>
- [6] Chao, R. F. (2017). Using transformative learning theory to explore the mechanisms of citizen participation for environmental education on the removal of invasive species: The case of Green Island, Taiwan. *Eurasia Journal of Mathematics, Science and Technology Education*, 13(6), 2665–2682. <https://doi.org/10.12973/EURASIA.2017.01246A>
- [7] Daramola, M. O. (2018). Enhancement of Transformative Learning in Large Classes of Learners in Engineering Education. *IOP Conference Series: Materials Science and Engineering*, 413(1). <https://doi.org/10.1088/1757-899X/413/1/012026>
- [8] Dix, M. (2016). The Cognitive Spectrum of Transformative Learning. *Journal of Transformative Education*, 14(2), 139–162. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1541344615621951>
- [9] Fadli, A., Amalia, F., Novirsari, E., Amelia, R., & Muhammad Fathoni. (2021). The Influence Of Marketing Communications On Loyalty Through Satisfaction. *Business and Management Review*, 2(12), 850–860. <https://doi.org/10.47153/jbmr212.2982021>
- [10] Haris, A., Samosir, H. E., & Lubis, S. H. (2023). Marketing Communications as Strategy Expanding Market Share In Era 4 . 0. *International Journal of Social Science and Business*, 7(1), 188–198.
- [11] Iafate, M. (2018). *The Embodied Experience and Transformative Learning: Moving Towards a Healthy and Empowered Self*. <https://doi.org/10.11575/PRISM/33065>
- [12] Iswati, H., Iqbal, M., Mudatsir, A., Brabo, N. A., & Meidiyustiani, R. (2023). HOW MARKETING COMMUNICATION AFFECT CONSUMER PURCHASE INTENTION IN SOCIAL MEDIA CONTEXT (CASE STUDY : INDONESIAN MSMES BUSINESS). *International Journal of Social Service and Research*, 03(01), 142–150.
- [13] Kaowiwattanakul, S. (2020). Role of transformative learning in developing global mindedness in an EFL literature studies context. *Journal of Asia TEFL*, 17(2), 508–522. <https://doi.org/10.18823/asiatefl.2020.17.2.13.508>
- [14] Katti, C., & Barbosa, B. (2023). Customers ' Perspectives on Promotion-Based , Permission-Based , and Service-Oriented E-Mail Marketing Strategies : A Qualitative Study. *International Journal of Marketing, Communication and New Media*, 11(December), 5–26.
- [15] Madan, A., & Rosca, M. I. (2022). Current Trends in Digital Marketing Communication. *Journal of Marketing Research and Case Studies*, 2022.
- [16] Makgopa. (2022). Barriers in Planning and Implementing of Marketing Communication Strategies. *IPRPD International Journal of Business & Management Studies*, 03(04), 40–47.
- [17] Marpurdianto, K., & Kusuma, A. P. D. (2022). MARKETING COMMUNICATION ONLINE STRATEGY OF CV. MULTICRAFT INDONESIA. *Equilibrium*, 18(2), 122–125.
- [18] McRae, N. (2015). Exploring conditions for transformative learning in work-integrated education. *Asia-Pacific Journal of Cooperative Education*, 16(2), 137–144.
- [19] Meerts-Brandsma, L., Sibthorp, J., & Rochelle, S. (2020). Using transformative learning theory to understand outdoor adventure education. *Journal of Adventure Education and Outdoor Learning*, 20(4), 381–394. <https://doi.org/10.1080/14729679.2019.1686040>
- [20] Mohamad Abdel-Haq, E., Mohamad Al-Hadi, T., & Ghanem Mohammad, S. (2019). A Transformative Learning-Based Strategy for Developing Critical Reflection and Reflective Writing Skills of Secondary School EFL Students. *Journal of Faculty of Education*, 119(2), 1–39. <https://doi.org/10.21608/jfeb.2019.61316>

- [21] Muttaqin, M. T., Fauziyah, A., Yusuf, I., & Rachmani, N. N. (2022). Analysis of Marketing Communication Strategies in Increasing Sales Volume Of A.M Production House During the Covid-19 Outbreak. *A Social Science and Entrepreneurship Journal*, 1(1), 13–18.
- [22] Pahlevi, R. W., & Nurcahyo, N. (2022). SYSTEMATIC ANALYSIS OF INTEGRATED MARKETING COMMUNICATION RESEARCH. *Manajemen Pemasaran*, 16(2), 104–114. <https://doi.org/10.9744/pemasaran.16.2.104>
- [23] Permatasari, I., & Adinugraha, H. H. (2021). Marketing communication strategy in increasing sales of pottery products. *Indonesian Journal of Islamic Economics Research*, 3(2), 73–82.
- [24] Purnomo, D., Edward, Y. R., Syaifuddin, & Sofiyan. (2019). The Effect Of Marketing Communications Strategy And Promotion On Customer Loyalty With Customer Satisfaction As A Moderating Variable In Pt . Bank Rakyat Indonesia Tbk Especially In Work Units Kcp Diski Year 2019. *International Journal Of Science, Technology & Management*, 319–324.
- [25] Ristina. (2014). Transformative learning theory and coaching: Application in practice. *International Journal of Evidence Based Coaching & Mentoring*, 8, 39–53.
- [26] Rizaldi, A., & Hidayat, H. (2020). Digital Marketing Communication Strategy. *Jurnal Entrepreneur Dan Entrepreneurship*, 9(2), 57–66. <https://doi.org/10.37715/jee.v9i2.1340>
- [27] Satriawan, K., & Purnama, W. (2022). Marketing Communication Strategies to Attract Consumer Interest During the Covid-19 Pandemic in Halfway Puri. *Advances in Social Science, Education and Humanities Research*, 655(Ticash 2021), 1215–1220.
- [28] Schnitzler, T. J. (2020). *Success factors of transformative learning for sustainable development*. https://www.oefse.at/fileadmin/content/Downloads/Publikationen/Foren/forum75_schnitzler_web.pdf
- [29] Sims, J. D., & CUNLIFF, E. (2022). Transformative Learning in Our Past and Future : A Retrospective Review toward Greater Heights. *Journal of Transformative Learning*, 9(1).
- [30] SIVAGNANAM, S. D. (2016). *TRANSFORMATIVE LEARNING EXPERIENCES AMONG INTERNATIONAL POSTGRADUATE STUDENTS IN THE CLASSROOM CONTEXTS*.
- [31] Susanti, C. E., Srimulyani, V. A., Hermanto, Y. B., Anang, L., & Waloyo, S. (2023). Building public satisfaction with marketing communication strategy and service quality. *Manajemen Komunikasi*, 7(2), 136–156.
- [32] Zein, D., & Wagiati. (2023). The Effect of Marketing Communication Strategies Through Celebgrams on Perceptions of the Product among Indonesian Millennials. *Komunikasi*, 15(1), 74–90.